

Cultural clash and solipsism in the works of Henry James

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Abstract: *In this present article, I would like to expound on how conspicuously, the novels of Henry James zero on “Relevance in cultural clash and solipsism. In general, in the thread of characters, it is quite apparent and in particular, through the protagonists, the cultural clash and solipsism are made glaring by adroit penning of Henry James as the the thread of characters travel through the pages of novels and novellas. And I want to stress on how, as a matter of factly, Henry being nostalgic, in the beauty and dignity of art, wants to recall the memory, which is ever verdurous through the most pivotal characters , and how the true hues of human nature are expressly exposed to bring awareness about the inherent human nature; vividly discuss various global issues, which have become the bone of contention even in the so called Global Village and how the selfishness is predominantly detrimental to the augmentation of humanity.*

Keywords: *Cultural Clash, Solipsism, dignity of art, estrangement and emigration.*

Introduction

Henry James, who belonged to 19th century and 20th century is said to be a great transitional figure between literary realism and literary modernism. He was the son of Henry James Sir and brother of William James and diarist Alice James. William James is the best known for ‘the stream of Consciousness’ and Alice James is best known for the ‘diary writing’. All his themes deal with the social and marital issues among emigre Americans, the English and continental Europeans. All his works like *The Portrait of a Lady*; *The Ambassadors*; *The Wings of the Dove* and *The Golden Bowl*, *The Portrait of a*

Lady are experimental in nature. “*Though the image of a dove has traditional associations with love and peaceful harmony, specific reference to a dove's wings may connote wealth or money*”¹

The Works and the crucial themes

In the portrait of a lady, the story is about the strongwilled young women. Isabel Archer, who becomes a victim with Machiavellianism by two American expatriates. Machiavellianism is a personality trait characterised by interpersonal manipulation, indifference to morality, the lack of empathy and a

focus on self interest. The psychologists Richard Christie and Florence Geis named the trait after Niccolò Machiavelli, as they used the truncated statements inspired by his works to study variations in human behaviours. It is one of the dark triad traits, along with the subclinical versions of narcissism and psychopathy. Isabel Archer, a New Yorker is invited by Lydia Touchett, on the invitation of Lydia to meet her husband, Daniel at his estate near London. Later Isabel declines Warburton's sudden proposal of marriage. She also rejects the hand of Casper Goodwood. In fact, she is drawn towards him but her commitment to independence make her decline this proposal and she thinks that it would sacrifice her freedom she feels, in which novel, the themes like selfishness, broken families, treasury, adulterous real ships, estrangement and emigration are deeply discussed.

The Ambassadors is another novel written by Henry James, Henry James got the idea for *The Ambassadors* from his friend, novelist, William Dean Howell, novelist. In the novel, Lewis Lambert Strether is the protagonist, who is the most cultured man in his fifties and he makes a trip to Europe to bring the son of his widowed fiancée 'Bach' to family business. We have a fictional town of Woollett. The protagonist is a cultured man in his fifties. He also goes to Paris to find Chad, the wayward son of his fiancé, Mrs. Newsome, the novel beautifully chronicles his change from American to Europe. This is the place where he has inappropriate romantic liaison and vulgar adventures. If Strether does not bring Chad back, his engagement with Mrs. Newsome would be at risk.

The theme of liberation from a cramped, almost starved, emotional life into a more generous and gracious existence throughout *The Ambassadors*.

The Wings of Dove speaks about Kate Croy and Merton Densher, who are two betrothed Londoners and who desperately want to marry but have very little money. Kate is constantly put upon by family troubles, and is now living with her domineering aunt, Maud Lowder. Into their world comes Milly Theale, an enormously rich young American woman who had previously met and fallen in love with Densher, although she has never revealed her feelings. Her travelling companion and confidante, Mrs. Stringham, is an old friend of Maud. Kate and Aunt Maud welcome Milly to London, and the American heiress enjoys great social success. The lovers part on the novel's final page with a cryptic exclamation from Kate: "We shall never be again as we were!"

The Golden Bowl is a 1904 novel by Henry James. Set in England, this complex, intense study of marriage. The novel focuses deeply and almost exclusively on the consciousness of the central characters, with sometimes obsessive detail but also with powerful insight.

The Turn of the Screw is an 1898 horror novella by Henry James. *The Turn of the Screw* is considered a work of both Gothic and horror fiction. One of the central conflicts in the novella is the potential corruption of the two children under the care of the governess. Another important novel is *The Europeans: A sketch*, a short novel by Henry James in 1878. A comedy contrasting the behaviour and attitudes of the two visitors from Europe with

those of their relatives living in the new world of New England. The tale opens in Boston and New England in the middle of the 19th century, and describes the experiences of two European siblings shifting from the old to the new world. A passionate Pilgrim is a novella by Henry James published in 1871. The story was set in England, the tale shows James' strong interest in the contrast between the Old World and the New. In fact, the difference between America and Europe erupts into open conflict in the story, which leads to an ironic ending.

Madame de Mauves is a novella by Henry James, was originally published in *Galaxy* magazine in 1874. The story beautifully centers on the troubled marriage of a scrupulous American wife and a far from scrupulous French husband, and is told mostly from the point of view of a male friend of the wife.

Daisy Miller is a novella by Henry James that first appeared in *The Cornhill Magazine* in June–July 1878, and in book form the following year. It clearly portrays the courtship of the beautiful American girl Daisy Miller by Winterbourne, a sophisticated compatriot of hers. His pursuit of her is hampered by her own flirtatiousness, which is frowned upon by the other expatriates when they meet in Switzerland and Italy. This novella serves as both a psychological description of the mind of a young woman and as an analysis of the traditional views of a society where she is a clear outsider. Henry James uses Daisy's story to discuss what he thinks Europeans and Americans believe about each other and more generally the prejudices common in any culture.

The Aspern Papers is a novella by American writer Henry James, originally published in *The Atlantic Monthly* in 1888, with its first book publication later in the same year. One of James's best-known and most acclaimed longer tales, *The Aspern Papers* is based on the letters Percy Bysshe Shelley wrote to Mary Shelley's stepsister, Claire Clairmont, who saved them until she died. Set in Venice, *The Aspern Papers* demonstrates James's ability to generate suspense while never neglecting the development of his characters. *The Lesson of the Master* is a novella written by Henry James, originally published in 1888.

The novella tells the story of a young writer, Paul Overt, who meets Henry St. George, a famous novelist Overt admires. During that time, Overt also meets and falls in love with Marian Fancourt, a young woman who admires both St. George's and Overt's work. During their meetings, St. George, who is married, advises Overt against getting married and having children, arguing that a wife and children will be the death of Overt's creativity and career. Overt then takes an extended vacation in which he considers St. George's advice. When he returns, he learns that St. George's wife had died and that St. George and Marian Fancourt had become engaged. Overt feels that St. George had set him up in order to have Miss Fancourt for himself, but St. George insists that by marrying her, he saved Overt and his career.

The Beast in the Jungle is a 1903 novella by Henry James, first published as part of the collection *The Better Sort*. Almost universally considered one of James' finest short narratives, this story treats appropriately universal themes: loneliness, fate, love and death. The

parable of John Marcher and his peculiar destiny has spoken to many readers who have speculated on the worth and meaning of human life.

In the Cage is a novella by Henry James, first published as a book in 1898. This long story centers on an unnamed London telegraphist. She deciphers clues to her clients' personal lives from the often cryptic telegrams they submit to her as she sits in the "cage" at the post office. Sensitive and intelligent, the telegraphist eventually finds out more than she may want to know. *Partial Portraits* is a book of literary criticism by Henry James published in 1888. The book collected essays that James had written over the preceding decade, mostly on English and American writers. But the book also offered treatments of Alphonse Daudet, Guy de Maupassant and Ivan Turgenev. Perhaps the most important essay was *The Art of Fiction*, James' plea for the widest possible freedom in content and technique in narrative fiction. "*The unnamed protagonist of In the Cage can be seen as a version of the Jamesian artist, constructing a complex finished work from the slightest hints.*"

Conclusion

The most of the characters in his works deal with the diverse internal states of the mind and the social dynamics *The Portrait of a Lady* was published in 1881, and it was regarded as the finest novel. Very glaring themes that are reflected in his novels are freedom, responsibility and betrayal. Interestingly, all his works are set in Europe, mostly England and Italy. Henry James is more interested in the differences in the new world and the old one. thus, the estrangement, emigration, love for foreign living, family relationships, treacherous relationships,

broken bonds, the marked differences of living in both the countries through beautiful characterisation has been outlined beautifully. Through all his works, the similar theme recurs in the pages of the novels through the complex relationships, enigmatic themes and beautiful language embedded.

The works cited

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Wings_of_the_Dove
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/In_the_Cage